

MEMORANDUM

SUBJECT: OPPOSITION TO THE “PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL, 2021”

Submitted to:

The Clerk to the Committee
The Committee on Constitutional, Legal, and Parliamentary Affairs
Office of Parliament, Osu - Accra, Ghana

Submitted by:

Date:

25th September, 2021.

MEMORANDUM
OPPOSITION TO THE “PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND
GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL, 2021”

With respect to your advertisement in the Daily Guide Newspaper on 9th September, 2021, I am grateful for the opportunity as a citizen of Ghana to submit this memorandum to your honourable committee.

My name is K██████ M██████, and I write to register my opposition to the “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021” and call on the Parliament to reject the Bill.

I wish to draw the attention of the committee to the unconstitutional nature of the “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021” (hereafter referred to as the ‘Bill’), and the fact that the Bill goes against our founding national principles of “Freedom and Justice”, which we proudly emblazon on our Coat of Arms and other national emblems.

Chapter Five of the Constitution of Ghana enshrines the fundamental human rights and freedoms of all Ghanaians. In particular, the Bill goes against constitutional rights and freedoms such as “Respect for Human Dignity”, “Equality and Freedom from Discrimination”, and “Protection of Privacy” (Articles 12, 15, 17, and 18)

Thus, members of the LGBTQIA+ community in Ghana have their fundamental human rights guaranteed by the constitution so far as they are consenting adults harming no other people by their lives and activities. Parliament should not infringe on these rights and freedoms.

Our nation’s founders fought long and hard to guarantee our freedom from the injustices of colonial rule, imperialism, and racism. We must honour the “Freedom and Justice” referenced on our Coat of Arms that so many people lost their lives for by ensuring freedom and justice for all Ghanaians, whether or not we agree with their ways of life.